

STUDIES ON THE NATURE OF THE RACEMIC MODIFICATIONS OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN SOLID STATE. PART XVI.

p-SULPHONAMIDO-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-METHOXY-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-ETHOXY-PHENYLIMINOCAMPHORS (*d*- & *dl*-) AND *p*-SULPHONAMIDO-*o*- AND *p*-METHOXY-PHENYLAMINOCAMPHORS (*d*- & *dl*-)

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The nature of the racemic forms of *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-ethoxy-phenyliminocamphors and *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*- and *p*-methoxy-phenylaminocamphors has been studied by the application of the melting point-composition method of Roozeboom. The racemic modifications of *o*- and *m*-ethoxyphenyliminocamphors have been found to be solid solutions giving single continuous curves with a central maximum, whereas the remaining forms are true *dl*-compounds of varying stability.

The nature of the racemic modifications of *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy-, and *o*-, *m*-, *p*-ethoxy-phenyliminocamphors and *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*- and *p*-methoxy-phenylaminocamphors has been discussed in the present communication by studying the freezing point-composition diagrams based on the method adopted by Roozeboom (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 537; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 28, 494). It is observed that if the melting point-composition diagram is composed of (i) three curves, the racemic modification is a true *dl*-compound, (ii) two curves, it is a conglomerate or mechanical mixture of equimolecular quantities of the *dextro* and *laevo* forms and (iii) one curve, a solid solution or mixed crystals of the active and opposite isomers in equimolecular proportions.

Whereas we have not met with any example of the racemic form existing as mechanical mixture, *o*- and *m*-ethoxyphenylimino-*dl*-camphors are found to be solid solutions, and the racemic modifications of the remaining compounds are true *dl*-compounds.

Since each diagram is symmetrical, only the *dextro* forms together with the racemic modifications have been taken for the study: the half portion of each diagram is represented by *d-dl* and *dl-d* curves; the remaining part, *dl-l* and *l-dl*, represented by dotted curves, is drawn as a mirror image of the first half.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the racemic forms, with the exception of *p*-sulphonamidophenylimino-*dl*-camphor prepared by Singh and Manhas (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30A, 87), are new substances.

Amongst the *dextro* derivatives, the following are new compounds: *p*-sulphonamidophenylamino-*d*-camphor and *m*-methoxy-, *o*- and *m*-ethoxy-phenylimino-*d*-camphors. The physical properties and analyses of all the compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	The compounds and molecular formulae.	M.P.	Colour.	Cryst. form.	% Nitrogen Found, Calc.	Remarks
1.	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenylamino-camphors*, C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₃	<i>d</i> - 228° <i>dl</i> - 227.5°	Pale yellow Yellow	Thin rectangular plates Thin hexagonal plates	9.08 } 8.75 8.93 }	<i>A.</i> Solubility:—All the aryl-imino compounds are highly soluble in chloroform, acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene and pyridine; less so in methyl and ethyl alcohols and insoluble in water. While their solutions in benzene and pyridine are deep orange, in other solvents they are lemon-yellow. The aryl-imino compounds are fairly soluble in all organic solvents except <i>p</i> -sulphonamido-phenylamino-camphors in benzene in which they are almost insoluble.
2.	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenylamino-camphors, C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₃	<i>d</i> - 181.5° <i>dl</i> - 185.5°	Colorless Colorless	Long prismatic needles Rectangular plates	9.10 } 8.70 8.95 }	
3.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	<i>d</i> -** 120° <i>dl</i> - 118°	Yellow Yellow	Leaflets Leaflets	5.54 } 5.33 }	
4.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	<i>d</i> - 78.5° <i>dl</i> - 97.5°	Yellow Golden yellow	Silky needles Cubes	5.33 } 5.41 }	
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	<i>d</i> -‡ 114.5° <i>d</i> -§ 120° <i>dl</i> - 130°	Yellow Golden yellow Golden yellow	Leaflets Prismatic needles Hexagonal plates	5.29 } 5.44 }	
6.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	<i>d</i> -§ 148° <i>dl</i> - 134°	Colorless Colorless	Long shining needles Prismatic needles	... } 5.37 }	<i>B.</i> Liquid compounds:—The <i>m</i> -methoxyphenylamino-camphors (<i>d</i> and <i>dl</i>) and also the <i>o</i> -, <i>m</i> - and <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenylamino-camphors (<i>d</i> and <i>dl</i>) were prepared by the usual methods, but being liquids, they could not be included in the present study.
7.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	<i>d</i> -‡ 101° <i>dl</i> - 108.5°	Colorless Colorless	Thin plates Plates	5.38 } 5.40 }	
8.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	<i>d</i> - 53° <i>dl</i> - 59°	Bright yellow Bright yellow	Leaflets Leaflets	5.16 } 5.19 }	
9.	<i>m</i> -Ethoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	<i>d</i> - 82.5° <i>dl</i> - 120.5°	Yellow Deep yellow	Pine needles Prismatic needles	5.14 } 5.18 }	<i>C.</i> Melting points:—The melting point of <i>p</i> -sulphonamidophenylamino- <i>d</i> -camphor has been reported by Singh and Manhas* to be 240°, whereas we find it to be 227.5°. Similarly the melting point of <i>o</i> -methoxyphenylamino- <i>d</i> -camphor, reported 125-26° by Singh and Mazumdar**, was found to be 120°.
10.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenylamino-camphors, C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	<i>d</i> -‡ 112° <i>dl</i> - 111°	Bright yellow Golden yellow	Silky leaflets Prismatic needles	... } 5.18 }	

* Singh and Manhas (*loc. cit.*).** Singh and Mazumdar (*loc. cit.*).‡ Forster and Thornley (*loc. cit.*).§ Singh, R.K. *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 417, 986.

The different *imino* compounds were prepared by condensing the camphorquinones (*d*- and *dl*-) with the following bases: *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-anisidines and *o*-, *m*-, *p*-phenetidines, by one of the two methods described below.

(a). *Condensation of the Free Base with Camphorquinone*.—The free base, with an equimolecular quantity of camphorquinone (*d*- or *dl*-) was heated in the presence of an excess of anhydrous sodium sulphate in an oil-bath at 120-40° for 12 to 16 hours. The product was extracted with water and the residue crystallised from rectified spirit. This method was unsuccessful in the case of *o*- and *m*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphors and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-ethoxy-phenyliminocamphors (*d*- and *dl*-).

(b). *Condensation of the Hydrochloride of the Base with Camphorquinone*.—This method, much more effective than the first, consisted in heating equimolecular quantities of camphorquinone (*d*- or *dl*) and the hydrochloride of the base with an excess of fused sodium acetate on a water-bath for 2 to 4 hours. The product was washed with water and the yellow-coloured residue crystallised from alcohol. This method was applicable for all the compounds except in the case of *p*-sulphonamidophenyliminocamphors (*d*- and *dl*-) where the hydrochloride could not be prepared due to insolubility of the base in ether and other organic solvents.

A marked difference in the reactivity of *d*- and *dl*-camphorquinones was observed. The *dl*-camphorquinone was found to be more reactive than the *d*-form by the comparatively short time required for condensation. Whereas *dl*-camphorquinone condensed easily with *o* and *m*-anisidines by the free base method, *d*-camphorquinone did not; for the preparation of *o*- and *m*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphors therefore, the hydrochloride method was applied.

The aryl-*amino* derivatives were prepared by reduction of the corresponding *imino* compounds by the following two methods:

The acid reduction gave generally poor yields as in the case of *p*-methoxyphenylamino-*d*-camphor, prepared by Forster and Thornley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 952). The alkaline reduction method was therefore applied in all the cases, except in the case of *p*-sulphonamidophenylaminocamphors (*d*- and *dl*-) where the *amino* compounds were insoluble in ether.

p-Sulphonamidophenylaminocamphors (*d*- and *dl*-) were prepared by the acid reduction method of Forster and Thornley (*loc. cit.*).

The *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenylaminocamphors (*d*- and *dl*-) were prepared by the alkaline reduction method after Singh and Mazumder (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 566).

p-Methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor exists in dimorphic forms (Table I). Both the forms were prepared in the same way except for some difference in crystallisation of the crude product. Recrystallisation from absolute or 90% aqueous alcohol gave the β -form (m.p. 120°), while more dilute alcohol solutions (about 50%) deposited the α -form (m.p. 114.5°).

Mutual Transformation of α - and β -Forms

(i). α -Form was converted into β -form by recrystallisation from absolute or 90% alcohol.

(ii). α -Form changed into β -form by heating it at its melting point with a trace of β -form.

(iii). α -Form on being kept in molten state for sometime gave β -form.

(iv). β -Form on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol (50%) gave α -form.

DISCUSSION

Nature of the Racemic Forms

p-Sulphonamidophenylimino- and -aminocamphors.—The melting point—composition diagrams of the aryl-iminocamphors (Fig. 1-a) and the corresponding amino-

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

camphors (Fig. 1-b) consist of three curves, DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L , in each case with a central maximum R and two sharp and well-defined eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 ; this shows that the racemic forms of both the compounds are true *dl*-compounds.

In the case of *aryl-amino* compound (Fig. 1-b), the *dl-d* curve is steep, showing that the *dl*-compound is stable and does not dissociate appreciably at its melting point, whereas the *dl-d* curve of the *aryl-imino* derivative is practically flat, specially in the region 50*d* : 50*dl* to 30*d* : 70*dl*, indicating a tendency to form solid solutions between the *dextro* and *racemic* isomers in this region.

The *aryl-amino* racemate is much more stable than the corresponding *imino* derivative as the area under the central part of the diagram is much greater in the former than in the latter.

FIG. 3

o-Methoxyphenylimino- and -aminocamphors.—The diagrams of each of these compounds (Fig. 2-a and 2-b) consist of three curves, DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L with a central maximum R, indicating these racemic forms to be true *dl*-compounds. The central portions of these diagrams are almost similar in shape, occupying relatively small areas and the *dl-d* curves are steep; these racemic forms are therefore stable at the melting point, but the range of stability is not large, being lower in *imino* than in the corresponding *amino* derivative.

In the case of the *imino* compound (Fig. 2-a), the *d-dl* curve is horizontal in the range 60*d* : 40*dl* to 40*d* : 60*dl*; this points to the fact that the racemic compound and the optically active form give solid solutions in this region. Both the diagrams, however, have sharp and well-defined eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 .

p-Methoxyphenylimino- and -aminocamphors.—The diagrams of these compounds (Fig. 3-a and 3-b) consist of three curves with a central maximum point as in the case of *ortho* and *meta* compounds; the racemic forms are therefore true *dl*-compounds. In both the diagrams, the *dl-d* curves are steep and the areas covered by the central portions large, being greater in *imino* than in the corresponding *amino* derivative. This shows that the racemic compounds are stable over a considerable range, which is, however, greater in the *imino* derivative than in the *amino* racemate. Whereas in the case of aryl-aminocamphors (Fig. 3-b) the

FIG. 4

central top portion of the curve is quite pointed, showing practically no dissociation of the racemic form; in the case of the corresponding *iminocamphors* (Fig. 3-a), this part is somewhat rounded, indicating that the racemic compound dissociates, to some extent, to the optically active and opposite forms near its melting point.

The *p*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor exists in dimorphic forms (α and β).

These forms are mutually interconvertible as described in the experimental part. The racemic modification with each of these α - and β -forms gives identical and superposable curves (Fig. 3-a). This shows that the *transition temperature* is below the melting points of the mixtures (Singh and Seth, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 491; Singh and Verma *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1956, **48A**, 21).

m-Methoxyphenyliminocamphors.—This diagram (Fig. 4-a) is made up of three curves, DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L with a central maximum R, showing that the racemic form is a true *dl*-compound. The steep slope of the *dl*-*d* curve and the large area occupied by the central part of the diagram indicate that the *dl*-compound is stable over a wide range. No sharp and well-defined eutectic points can be observed at E_1 and E_2 ; this shows that the racemic compound has a tendency to form solid solutions with the active form in this region.

o-, *m*- & *p*-Ethoxyphenyliminocamphors.—Whereas the melting point—composition diagrams of *ortho* (Fig. 4-c) and *meta* (Fig. 4-b) isomers consist of single continuous curves with a maximum, indicating these racemic modifications to be solid solutions of equimolecular quantities of the *dextro* and *laevo* forms, that of the *para* isomer (Fig. 3-c) consists of three curves, DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L with a central maximum R and two sharp and well-defined eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 ; the racemic form in this case is therefore a true *dl*-compound. As the central part of the diagram occupies a fairly large area, the range of stability of the racemic compound is considerable.

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